

Alumina Gel as a Desulphurising Agent in Petroleum Refining.

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It is proposed to deal in this paper with the suitability of alumina gel for refining mineral oils containing sulphur compounds. The character and quantity of the sulphur compounds present in different oils vary according to the nature of the oil, certain American, Mexican and Persian mineral oils, brown coal and shale oils and cracked petroleum being particularly rich in sulphur compounds which not only cause colour and smell to the distillates but are largely responsible for corrosion, specially in internal combustion engines. Their removal is therefore a matter of importance for the refiner.*

Various methods, both chemical and physical in nature, are followed in large scale practice for the removal of these undesirable sulphur compounds. Treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid or with sodium plumbite, heating with certain metals or their oxides and in recent years oxidation with sodium hypochlorite may be mentioned as the more important chemical methods while washing with liquid sulphur dioxide (Edeleanu process) and selective adsorption by silica gel are the physical methods that are used on a large scale for desulphurisation of mineral oils. The chemical methods are either inefficient or destructive of some of the other constituents of the oil while the Edeleanu process demands special appliances and technical skill and is unsuitable when small amounts of sulphur compounds are the only ingredients to be removed. The use of suitable adsorbents for the purpose, however, appears promising, owing to the simplicity with which they can be applied to large scale practice and to the low concentration in which sulphur compounds occur in petroleum distillates; for, according to Freundlich's adsorption isotherm, the use of adsorbents will be more effective in dilute rather than in concentrated solutions.

* It has been estimated (Editorial Notes, *J. Ind. & Eng. Chem.*, 1927, 19, 189) that in U. S. A. 50 million dollars would be saved annually if petrol containing more than 0.1% sulphur could be used.

Various adsorbents have been tried by different workers for their specific adsorption capacity on sulphur compounds. The use of silica gel for desulphurisation has been studied by Waterman and Perquin (*Chem. Wok. Blatt.*, 1925, 378) and by Wood, Shelley and Trusty (*J. Ind. & Eng. Chem.*, 1926, 18, 169) and since the war it has found increasing use in finely powdered or granular form as a desulphurising agent. The action of Fuller's earth and other naturally occurring or chemically activated silicates has been investigated by different authors and though they were efficient for removing colloidal dispersed materials, they were not found suitable for molecular dispersed substances. Activated carbon (Berl, *Zeit. ang. Chem.*, 1925, 39, 428) has been found more suitable when water is used as solvent and its use with petroleum distillates has been further restricted owing to the difficulty of its regeneration. The suitability of bauxite for desulphurisation has been studied by Dunstan, Thole and Remfry (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 179T) and it has been found to be a good decolourising and desulphurising agent.

In view of the large deposits of bauxite in India, further study of its properties as adsorbent seemed desirable. To begin with pure alumina gel prepared in the laboratory was selected for investigation and its capacity of selective adsorption for different types of sulphur compounds dissolved in "shell motor spirit," from which low boiling fractions were distilled off, was determined. The necessity for distilling off the low boiling fractions arose from the fluctuations in the rate of burning with changes in room temperature while estimating sulphur by the lamp method and also from the risk of handling ordinary petrol in the laboratory. The solvent was found to be practically free from sulphur, containing not more than 0.002% of the ingredient.

The following substances were used as sulphur compounds: Dimethyl sulphate, tolyl mustard oil, ethyl mercaptan, methyl sulphide, allyl mustard oil and a mixture of all these compounds, this mixture being termed in the following experiments as "mixture of sulphur compounds." Alumina gel, the preparation of which is described later, was added to the sulphurous oil in dry condition, shaken for 15 minutes and filtered. The removal of sulphur was determined by estimations before and after treatment.

Estimation of Sulphur.—The usual lamp method with some modifications was used for the estimation of sulphur. The difficulty

of maintaining a constant rate of burning necessitated an arrangement (1) to adjust the size of the flame when necessary without any loss of the solvent and (2) to protect the wickholder from variations in temperature. This consisted in placing the wickholder inside another short piece of glass tubing supported on a piece of rubber tubing as in Fig. 1. This outer tubing served as a jacket protecting the wickholder from variations in temperature and could also be raised or lowered regulating the size of the flame in case of necessity, which however arose very rarely owing to the protection of the wickholder. This arrangement suited the purpose admirably, provided the head of the wick was kept sufficiently low inside its holder to prevent any oil accumulating in the jacket.*

FIG. 1.

About 3 gm. of oil were burnt in the course of a couple of hours in a 50 c.c. conical flask carrying a cork and a jacketed glass tubing to serve as a wickholder as described above. The wick-head was kept below the top of the wickholder, the flame being slightly bigger than the size of a pea. The products of combustion were drawn by suction through two U-tubes containing sodium bicarbonate solution of known strength, the suction arms being filled with glass beads and provided with bulbs. The excess of alkali was titrated with hydrochloric acid, using methyl orange as indicator. Concordant results were obtained provided the same wick was not used for too long a time.

Preparation and Activation of Alumina Gel.

Aluminium hydroxide was obtained as a flocculent gelatinous precipitate by slow addition of ammonia under vigorous stirring

* The suggestion for regulating the flame by means of a sliding tube has also been made by Squire (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1926, 45, 466T.)

to a solution of aluminium sulphate or chloride, the temperature not exceeding 25°. It was found by Yoe (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2390) that a high temperature of precipitation is detrimental to the adsorptive power of the gel. This was washed free from all impurities and was obtained in a hard glass-like form by slow drying in an air-oven at 60-70°, activated by ignition and consequent dehydration. As regards the suitable temperature of roasting, there is however no unanimity. Perry (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 1462) used a temperature of 200°, Munro and Johnson (*Ind. and Eng. Chem.*, 1925, **17**, 88) activated alumina gel at 400°, Wood and others (*ibid.*, 1926, **18**, 1169) roasted at a temperature of 1000° while Dunstan and others (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, **43**, 179T) recommend 600-700° for bauxite. In view of these contradicting reports it was found necessary to investigate the optimum temperature of roasting and water content of the gel with reference to sulphur compounds. The results are noted in the following table.

TABLE I.

Solution taken:—50 c.c. containing mixture of sulphur compounds.
Quantity of adsorbent—2 gms.; Size—20/50 mesh.
Temp. of treatment—25°; Time of shaking—15 mins.

Temp. of roasting °C	Water in the gel %	Adsorbent in 50 c.c. soln. gms.	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of sulphur, %
75	44	2.3106	0.105	0.092	12.4
225-230	29	1.9408	..	0.079	24.8
280-290	19	2.045	..	0.071	32.4
350-400	6	2.1193	..	0.069	34.3
Dull red heat	...	1.913	..	0.074	29.5

In the above experiments the gel was heated for two hours to the required temperature in a paraffin-bath under slightly reduced pressure in a closed vessel to prevent contact with the fumes of the paraffin-bath and was cooled in a vacuum over P₂O₅ before use. It will be observed from the above table that the adsorption capacity rapidly increases with dehydration until the moisture content is 19%, further increase with dehydration being very slow, while too high a temperature is unfavourable. It is evident that the gel must be dry enough to have the capillary pores and the surface energy free but too drastic a drying would affect the structure of the gel and the size of the pores.

The unfavourable effect of high temperature of roasting has also been observed with other adsorbents. Ruff (*Chem. Zent.*, 1926, I, 1781. 2657, 2306, 605) has shown that the decrease in adsorption capacity of activated carbon by heating above 1000° is due to its slowly being converted into crystalline form. Kyropoulos (*Chem. Zent.*, 1917, II, 450) and Braesco (*Chem. Zent.*, 1919, I, 906) have shown that silica gel is partly converted into crystalline form by heating or standing for a long time. In case of alumina gel a similar transformation coupled with the collapse of the pores at too high a temperature is a probable explanation for its reduced activity.

Optimum Conditions for Desulphurisation.

A study of the optimum conditions to secure maximum desulphurisation by means of alumina gel as prepared above was then undertaken. It is well known that adsorption is influenced by various factors, namely, character and concentration of the sulphur compounds, quantity and size of particles of the adsorbent and temperature of treatment. The following experiments are therefore intended to find out the best conditions under which alumina gel should be allowed to act.

(a) Concentration of Sulphur Compounds.

As is to be expected from Freundlich's equation the percentages of sulphur compounds removed increase with dilution. That the process involved is essentially one of true adsorption may also be deduced from this application of Freundlich's equation :

$$\frac{x}{m} = Kc^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

where x/m = quantity adsorbed per gram of adsorbent ;

c = concentration of the solution in equilibrium with the adsorbed substance;

K and n are constants. n being greater than 1.

By plotting x/m against C , a curve of the nature of a parabola as shown in Fig. II is obtained.

FIG. II.

→ % of carbon or silica in the mixture. FIG. III.

- I. Curve for the mixture of alumina and carbon.
- II. Curve for the mixture of alumina and silica.

Taking the logarithms, the equation becomes

$$\log \frac{x}{m} = \frac{1}{n} \log c + \log K$$

In this form a straight line may be obtained by plotting $\log x/m$ against $\log c$.

The results obtained with variation in concentration are given in the following table.

TABLE II.

Solution taken:—40 c.c. containing methyl sulphide.

Adsorbent used:—4 gms., 50–100 mesh, at 25°C.

Time of shaking:—15 mins.

Initial conc. of S, %	Adsorbent gms.	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S, %	x/m	$\log x/m$	$\log c$
0.452	4.15	0.385	14.6	0.0161	-1.7932	-0.4145
0.179	3.20	0.148	17.5	0.0097	-2.0132	-0.8297
0.091	3.85	0.068	25.2	0.006	-2.2218	-1.1675
0.069	4.7	0.046	33.3	0.0049	-2.3098	-1.3372
0.026	3.3	0.017	34.6	0.0027	-2.5686	-1.7696

TABLE III.

Conditions same as in Table II, but with different sulphur compounds.

Sulphur compounds.	Initial conc. %	Final conc. %	Removal of sulphur, %
Benzyl mercaptan	0.443	0.397	10.6
	0.125	0.105	16.0
	0.081	0.056	30.0
Allyl mustard oil	0.291	0.245	15.8
	0.130	0.102	21.5
Tolyl mustard oil	0.165	0.136	17.6
	0.059	0.036	38.9

(b) *Quantity of the Adsorbent.*

It will be seen from the following table that the percentage of sulphur removal increases with the quantity of adsorbent used. But the fact that a considerable amount of the solvent is adsorbed and also held mechanically by the adsorbent makes it desirable that its use should be limited to the lowest effective amount.

TABLE IV.

Sulphur compound used:—Tolyl mustard oil.

Other conditions same as in previous table.

Quantity of adsorbent in 40 c.c. in gms.	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S, %
0.98	0.087	0.084	...
3.2	"	0.074	15
13	"	0.04	54

(c) *Size of Particles.*

It has been found that silica gel in granular form as prepared by Maschinenfabrik Fr. Herrmann, G.m.b.H. (Germany) is particularly suitable for use as adsorbent (Koetschan, *Zeit. ang. Chem.*, 1926, 40, 210). In the case of alumina gel 50/160 mesh is found to be the most suitable size as will be seen from the following table. It is likely that the size of the pores are affected when very finely powdered though a larger surface thereby becomes available. The size of the particles will naturally influence the choice of the method of filtration, the large particles being more suitable for column filtration and regeneration by means of steam and air while finely powdered adsorbent has to be stirred with the oil with subsequent filtration and regeneration by means of extraction with solvents. The loss due to dust formation is also considerable.

TABLE V.

Sulphur compound:—Tolyl mustard oil.

Adsorbent:—2.8 gms. in 40 c.c. solution.

Temperature and time of shaking same as before.

Size of particles, mesh per sq. in.	Adsorbent per 40 c.c., gm.	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S, %
10-20	2.76	0.087	0.073	16.1
20-50	2.75	..	0.071	18.4
50-160	2.65	..	0.069	20.7
less than 160 mesh	3.2	..	0.074	15.0

(d) *Temperature of Treatment.*

It will be observed from the following table that a high temperature favours desulphurisation though this is contrary to the usual gaseous adsorption phenomenon. Increased desulphurisation with rise of temperature has also been observed by Dunstan, Thole and Remfry (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 179T) in the case of bauxite. According to them, polymerisation and in some cases partial decomposition takes place, specially at a high temperature and the products are then more easily removed by adsorption.

TABLE VI.

Sulphur compound :—Tolyl mustard oil.

Size of particles :—20/50 mesh.

Other conditions same as before.

Solvent.	Adsorbent in gms.	Temp. of treatment. °C	Time of contact (mins.)	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc.	Removal of S, %
Petrol	2.76	25.0	15	0.072	0.058	19.4
..	2.23	100	60	..	0.05	30.6
Kerosene	2.5	25	15	0.083	0.068	18.1
..	2.62	140	60	..	0.055	33.7

(e) *Types of Sulphur Compounds.*

The following table indicates the power of selective absorption of alumina gel for different types of sulphur derivatives. The remarkably high adsorption of dimethyl sulphate (75%) even in fairly concentrated solution indicates that here the basic nature of the adsorbent comes into play. A neutral adsorbent, activated carbon (Kahlbaum) was tried on dimethyl sulphate under the same conditions as with alumina and showed only 25.7% S-removal.

TABLE VII.

Sulphur compounds.	Initial conc. %	Final conc. %	Removal %
Dimethyl sulphate	0.266	0.066	75
Tolyl mustard oil	0.0585	0.036	38.5
Hydrogen sulphide	0.08	0.068	15
Benzyl mercaptan	0.0814	0.0565	30.6
Methyl sulphide	0.0914	0.0675	26.2
Allyl mustard oil	0.13	0.102	21.5
Ethyl mercaptan	0.051	0.04	21
Elementary sulphur	0.097	0.093	...
Carbon Disulphide	0.098	0.098	...
Phenyl mustard oil	0.14	0.129	7.8
Mixture of S-compounds	0.105	0.079	24.8

Note :—The concentration of the S-compounds should be borne in mind while comparing the results given in the last column.

Catalytic Oxidation of Sulphur Compounds with Atmospheric Air.

The high percentage of removal in the case of dimethyl sulphate led to the following attempts for the oxidation of sulphur compounds before adsorption. As already mentioned, sulphur compounds are now oxidised on a large scale by means of sodium hypochlorite and are removed by subsequent washing and adsorption. The preparation of a reagent of suitable alkalinity and available chlorine, the susceptibility of other constituents of the oil to the action of chlorine as also economic consideration suggest, if possible, the use of atmospheric air in place of the chemical reagent. In the following experiments, oxidation has been carried out by means of atmospheric air using alumina gel as a catalyser.

Alumina is known as a useful catalyser in many gas reactions such as oxidation of hydrogen sulphide, dehydration of alcohols and some other reactions. Badische Anilin und Soda Fabrik (D.-R. P., 405850) used alumina gel as a catalyser in the liquid phase for the oxidation of higher petroleum hydrocarbons. This is one of very few instances where alumina is used as a catalyser in liquid phase. When sulphur compounds are dissolved in petroleum, they resist oxidation with atmospheric air, being protected by surrounding hydrocarbons. Alumina gel however adsorbs the sulphur compounds on its surface and when atmospheric air is passed through makes direct contact with oxygen possible, thus facilitating the oxidation of the sulphur compounds.

The following experimental procedure was adopted:—The oil containing different S-compounds was taken in a round-bottomed flask and heated to about 150° in an oil-bath under reflux using two spiral condensers circulated with ice-cold water to prevent loss of the solvent due to evaporation, while air freed from carbon dioxide and moisture was passed through the heated oil for about a couple of hours at the rate of 20 litres per hour, about 4 gm. of alumina being used for every 50 c.c. of the oil. Owing to the loss of the solvent, it was necessary to conduct blank experiments under same conditions but without the use of any alumina in order to get a correct idea of the catalytic action of the gel. The oil was then cooled and filtered and the amount of S-removal ascertained. In order to see if the hydrocarbons of the solvent were also oxidised by the above treatment, they were shaken with dilute alkali in a stoppered burette but no diminution in volume was detected. It may therefore be assumed that the solvent remains practically unaffected by the treatment. The results are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII.

Experiment.	S-com- pounds.	Alumina in 50 c.c. air blow- (gm.)	Rate of ing, lit- res per hr.	Time of treat- ment (mins.)	Temp. of treat- ment °C.	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S %
Without alumina	Benzyl mercaptan	0	20	90	160	0.085	0.104	...
With alu- mina	..	4	0.092	69.2
Without	0	15	150	150	0.284	0.319	...
With	4	0.130	59.2
Without ..	Free S	0	20	90	140	0.120	0.137	...
With	4	0.065	52.5
Without ..	Mixture of S-com- pounds	0	175	0.105	0.071	32.4
With	4.5	0.016	77.5
Without ..	Carbon- disulphide	0	160	0.092	0.038	58.7
With ..	Phenyl mustard oil	4	..	120	180	0.140	0.035	75.0

Note:—The concentration of S-compounds after passing air without the addition of alumina is taken as real initial concentration when calculating the percentage of S-removal with alumina as catalyser.

The results shown in this table are not however strictly comparable owing to variations in concentration and other factors. It will be noted that 60-80% of different S-compounds, depending on initial concentration and other factors, was removed by this treatment. These figures compare favourably with those obtained by sodium hypochlorite treatment (Birch and Norris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1934; Wood and others, *J. Ind. & Eng. Chem.*, 1926, 18). Elementary sulphur which is practically unaffected by the use of the adsorbent alone is removed to the extent of 52.5% in the course of one and a half hour. A comparison with Table VII will show a general increase in desulphurisation. If the solvent lost during the treatment be recovered, the process appears capable of large scale application, specially with those mineral oils which are poor in olefinic and other easily oxidisable hydrocarbons.

Effect of Mixtures of Alumina Gel with other Adsorbents.

It is well known that the presence of certain substances remarkably promotes the activity of catalysers and as a consequence mixtures are being increasingly used for catalysis, but instances of the use of mixtures for adsorption are very rare. Reyerson (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 88) observes that gases are better adsorbed by silica gel in the presence of very finely divided metals than by the gel alone. Fells and Firth (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1927, 41, 39T) state that slightly increased adsorption of benzene and toluene takes place when an intimate mixture of silica gel and carbon (from cane sugar) is used as adsorbent. Increased effect of silicalised carbon has also been observed by Berl (*loc. cit.*) though no figures are given to indicate the amount of increase. The German Patent No. 402488 mentions that a mixture of iron hydroxide with carbon effectively destroys the corrosive action of coal-distillates.

(a) Mixture of Alumina Gel with Activated Carbon.

Preparation.—An intimate mixture was obtained by suspending finely divided activated carbon (Kahlbaum) in a solution of aluminium sulphate and then precipitating the hydroxide by the addition of ammonia, drop by drop with constant stirring, the temperature not exceeding 25°. This was washed free from all impurities and after preliminary drying at 60°-70° it was obtained in the form of a hard glassy mass. This was powdered to 20/40 mesh, heated to 230°-235° for two hours and cooled in a desiccator before use.

The amount of carbon in the gel was approximately determined by ignition, the water content of the alumina dried at 230° being taken at 29% (Table I).

The results obtained with different percentages of activated carbon are shown in the following table. It will be observed that maximum efficiency is obtained with 21.7 % of carbon in the gel, the sulphur removed being 44.8 % against 24.7 % with pure alumina gel and 18.2 % with activated carbon.

TABLE IX.

S-compound :—Mixture of sulphur compounds.

Size :—40/50 mesh ; 2.4 gms. for 25 c.c. solution.

Time and temperature as usual.

% Carbon in adsorbent.	Quantity of adsorbent(gm.)	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S, %
0	2.4	0.105	0.079	24.7
6.5	2.4	..	0.068	35.2
21.7	2.38	..	0.058	44.8
43.4	2.41	..	0.067	36.2
55.8	2.4	..	0.079	24.7
66	2.39	..	0.081	22.8
100	2.38	..	0.086	18.1

(b) *Mixture of Alumina and Silica Gels.*

Preparation.—Silica gel was obtained by slowly adding hydrochloric acid to a solution of sodium silicate and washing free from impurities. This gel was suspended in a solution of aluminium sulphate and under constant stirring aluminium hydroxide was precipitated by slow addition of ammonia. This was dried as before first at 60°-70° and subsequently at 230°-235° for two hours. The percentage of silica in the mixture was determined gravimetrically after washing off the alumina with warm dilute nitric acid. The results obtained with different percentages of alumina and silica are shown in the following table.

TABLE X.

Conditions same as in previous table.

% Silica in the mixture.	Gms. adsorbent in 25 c.c.	Initial conc. of S, %	Final conc. of S, %	Removal of S, %
0.0	2.11	0.117	0.088	24.8
2.4	1.98	..	0. 83	29.1
23.7	2.05	..	0.047	60.0
63.7	2.12	..	0.070	40.2
100	1.95	..	0.094	20.0

It will be observed that the mixture with 23.7 % of silica adsorbs 60 % of S-compounds while the figures for pure alumina and silica gels are only 24.8 % and 20 % respectively. This enormous increase in the adsorption capacity does not seem to be due to any increase in surface area caused by precipitation of alumina on finely divided substances. Mixtures obtained by precipitating alumina on comparatively inert substances such as powdered glass or pumice stone, however, showed no increased adsorption capacity. This must therefore be attributed to the combination of pores of different sizes in the mixture. Further work in this line is being continued.

Regeneration of the Adsorbent.

The method of regenerating adsorbents by means of super-heated steam and air is also suitable in the case of alumina gel as will be evident from the following table. In spite of the basic nature of the gel, it does not apparently suffer any permanent reduction in its adsorption capacity and may be restored to almost its original activity.

TABLE XI.

Adsorbent:—Alumina gel used in previous experiments, 2 gm. for 25 c.c. solution.

S-compound :—Mixture of sulphur compounds.

Other conditions as usual.

Treatment of the adsorbent.	Initial S, %	Final S, %	Removal of S, %
Passed steam for two hrs. at 200° activated in paraffin-bath at 239°	0.105	0.086	18.1
Passed steam at 230° for 1/2 hr. then air at 230° for 1/2 hr. and again steam at 230° for the same period and finally activated at 230° for two hours.	...	0.078	25.7
Freshly prepared alumina activated at 230° for two hours.	...	0.079	24.8

In conclusion, it may be pointed out that the figures for desulphurisation given in the above tables are by no means the maximum attainable but depend on the quantity of the adsorbent used, concentration of S-compounds as well as on other factors. In column filtration, for example, the first fractions will be free from sulphur, the amount of which will however increase as the filtration proceeds.

Summary.

1. Sulphur in the oil has been estimated by the lamp method which has been suitably modified to give concordant results.

2. Optimum conditions for the activation of alumina gel, *i.e.*, the temperature of roasting and moisture content have been determined. Influence of other factors such as concentration and nature of S-compounds in the oil, quantity and size of particles of the adsorbent and temperature of treatment on adsorption has also been ascertained. Freundlich's adsorption isotherm has been found satisfactorily applicable.

3. Most of the sulphur compounds used have been satisfactorily removed by oxidation with atmospheric air, using alumina gel as a catalyser and subsequent filtration. This is an improvement on the present process of oxidation with sodium hypochlorite used on a large scale.

4. It has also been found that intimate mixtures of alumina gel with other adsorbents such as activated carbon or silica gel, specially the latter, mutually promote the adsorption capacity to a remarkable extent. This is similar to the action of promoters used in the preparation of catalysts.

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